

Performance and degradation analysis of sputter deposited thin-film platinum cathodes in PEM water electrolyzers analyzed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

Supplementary Information

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Figure S1: IV curves of cycle 4 of samples *MEA 240 μg* and *MEA 240 μg v2*. The graph demonstrates the high reproducibility of the sputter-etching treatment and magnetron sputtering process, confirming the consistency of the MEA with the best performance among all the samples tested.

Figure S2: IV-curves of MEAs with a Pt loading of $120 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ pair after the break-in period in cycle 4. The *MEA 120 μg* with a sputter-etched modified cathode outperformed its non-etched counterpart, achieving almost twice the performance.

Figure S3: The *MEA 240 μg* maintained stable performance throughout the measurement period. In contrast, low-loading MEAs, such as the depicted *MEA 30 μg* , exhibit a decline in performance over the same timeframe. In addition, as discussed in the main text, the IV curve of the *MEA 30 μg* in cycle 3 shows signs of mass transport limitation at voltages approaching 2.0 V. This feature diminishes over the course of the measurement.

Figure S4: Specific current density as a function of Pt loading. The specific current density j_{spec} was calculated by normalizing the current density j to the total noble metal loading, defined as the sum of iridium and platinum loading.

Figure S5: Time evolution of current densities normalized to their maximal value. Cycle 1 represents the cycle with the highest performance for each MEA. All data were measured at 2.0 V. While a significant performance decline is observed for most MEAs at 1.5 V (Fig. 5), the performance drop is considerably less pronounced at higher voltages.

Figure S6: a) Equivalent Electrical Circuit (EEC) used for the fitting the spectra. b) Example of a measured PEIS spectrum showing three distinguishable resistances: ohmic resistance R_{Ω} , cathodic charge transfer resistance R_c , and anodic charge transfer resistance R_a .

Figure S7: Time evolution of ohmic resistance for the *MEA 480 μg* and its non-etched counterpart, *MEA 480 μg plain*, at 1.45 V. The non-etched *MEA 480 μg plain* exhibits a rapid drop between the first and second cycle (the first data point is not shown), suggesting low porosity for hydrogen mass transport. However, after this initial change, the non-etched sample shows lower ohmic resistance, possibly due to better catalyst connectivity to the GDL.

Figure S8: Time evolution of cathodic capacitance of *MEA 480 μg* and its non-etched counterpart, *MEA 480 μg plain*, at 1.45 V. The etched *MEA 480 μg* exhibits several times higher capacitance, indicating that the sputter-etching treatment increases the active surface area of the catalyst.

Figure S9: The highest performance IV curves of *MEA 240 μg* and *MEA GDE* without and with ohmic drop correction ($U_{corr} = U - jR_{\Omega}$). The lower ohmic resistance of *MEA 240 μg* explains its superior performance compared to *MEA GDE*. After correcting for ohmic resistance, their performances become similar, with *MEA GDE* even outperforming *MEA 240 μg* at lower voltages.

Figure S10: Performance of *MEA 15 μg* over three cycles, shown without and with correction for ohmic resistance. The increase in ohmic resistance alone does not fully explain the observed performance degradation.

Charge transfer resistance and Tafel slope

Our system model consists of ohmic resistance and two electrodes (Fig. S5). It is common to describe the kinetics of each electrode using a logarithmic relationship between the overpotential η and current density j [1-3]:

$$\eta = b \log\left(\frac{j}{j_0}\right), \quad (\text{S1})$$

where parameter b is the Tafel slope, and j_0 is the exchange current density for the given electrode. Incorporating Ohm's law, the total cell voltage E can be expressed as [4, 5]:

$$E = E_0 + E_\Omega + \eta_c + \eta_a = E_0 + R_\Omega j + b_c \log\left(\frac{j}{j_{0,c}}\right) + b_a \log\left(\frac{j}{j_{0,a}}\right)$$

where $E_0 = 1.18 \text{ V}$ is the reversible electrolysis voltage at 80°C , the subscripts c, a denote the cathode and anode, respectively, and E_Ω accounts for the voltage drop due to the ohmic resistance R_Ω . The charge transfer resistance R for both electrode reactions is defined as [6, 7]:

$$R_c = \frac{d\eta_c}{dj} = \frac{b_c}{j \ln 10}, \quad R_a = \frac{d\eta_a}{dj} = \frac{b_a}{j \ln 10}.$$

Thus, plotting $1/R$ against j should give a linear dependence with a slope of $\ln 10/b$. By fitting these data, we can independently determine the Tafel slope for both the cathode and the anode (Fig. S10).

Additionally, the sum of b_c and b_a can be extracted from the IV characteristics. After correcting for the ohmic resistance, the kinetic voltage can be expressed as:

$$E_{\text{corr}} = E - R_{\Omega}j = (b_a + b_c) \log j + (E_0 - b_c \log j_{0,c} - b_a \log j_{0,a})$$

where the sum $b_a + b_c$ corresponds to the slope in a linear fit of voltage against the logarithm of current density (Fig. S11).

From the derived equations, it is evident that neither the corrected IV curves fitting nor the charge transfer resistance analysis allows us to determine the exchange current densities for the cathode and anode separately. However, the impedance spectroscopy analysis provides valuable insight into the processes inside the system by yielding the Tafel slopes.

Figure S11: Example of cathodic and anodic Tafel slope determination from charge transfer resistances for *MEA 60* μg in cycle 5.

Figure S12: Example of total Tafel slope determination from the IV curve for *MEA* 30 μg in cycle 7.

Figure S13: Time evolution of the anodic Tafel slopes. These values exhibited greater stability compared to the cathodic slopes. In cycle 4, water starvation of *MEA* 120 μg led to an unreliable data point that cannot be appropriately interpreted.

Figure S14: Time evolution of the Tafel slopes for the *MEA 30 μg*. The cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes, determined from charge transfer resistance analysis, are shown. Their sum is comparable to the Tafel slope obtained from the ohmic resistance corrected IV curves, confirming the consistency of the analysis.

Figure S15: Example of two distinct regimes with different Tafel slopes, with the transition current j_{trans} for *MEA 3.7 μg* in cycle 11.

References

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